

OPTIMISATION DESIGN OF FAST SIMULATION MODELS

29/08/2023

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ABSTRACT

The nearest future is very exciting for High Energy Physics, especially for the Large Hadron Collider experiments and the high-luminosity upgrade foreseen for 2029 and then say this will increase the demand for simulated data. As a response to resource challenges, which concern all full simulation methods, we propose a highly scalable framework for fast simulation methods. In this report, we present the development of the MLFastSim framework with the following ideas: semi-automatised design of a deep learning model (VAE) available in a distributed environment and integration of the system with an external tool for tracking training progress. Moreover, we also present in this report several additional improvements which increase the usability of the framework, and we identified the areas for the direction of further research and areas of the project's development.

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1 INTRODUCTION

In Large Hadron Collider (LHC) experiments, particle detectors measure particle properties when interacting with detectors' material. A calorimeter is a sub-detector to measure the energy of particles. Particles interact with the material of the calorimeter and create cascades of secondary particles called showers. Describing the behaviour of secondary particles (showers) relies on various simulation methods. Constrained by the need for accuracy, the detailed (full) particle simulation is slow and constitutes a bottleneck, hence there is a need for fast simulation methods.

Figure 1: Recent models show that there will be a very high demand for simulations in the near future. The plot presents various scenarios: baseline (intense), conservative and aggressive research. All three approaches exceed the budget (two solid black lines), and two of them are in a very significant way. Hence there is a big need for fast simulation methods.

As a response to resource challenges mention in Figure 1 multiple solutions have been proposed. All fast simulation methods rely on a direct inference of shower based on meta parameters like initial energy and angle of a particle and geometry of initial particle. In this approach, we do not need to simulate the creation of secondary particles.

2 GENERATIVE MODELS FOR FAST SIMULATION

2.1 Variational autoencoder used for generative modelling

In the last few years, generative models have gained more and more interest due to their application to many use cases. Relying on huge amounts of data, well-designed deep learning architectures have shown an incredible ability to produce highly realistic pieces of content of various kinds, such as images, texts, and sounds. Among these deep generative models, two major families stand out and deserve special attention: Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs) and Variational Autoencoders (VAEs).

A VAE is an artificial neural network architecture introduced by Diederik P. Kingma and Max Welling [8]. A VAE is an autoencoder whose encodings distribution is regularised during the training in order to ensure that its latent space has good properties allowing us to generate some new data.

2.2 Workflow

Most machine learning model development workflows follow the schema presented in Figure 2. The first step is to design and build a model based on prior knowledge, assumptions about the task and questions, to which we have a source of data. For instance, it is probably worth using convolutional layers if the input data are images. The available data is split into two disjoint sets - training data and test data. The reason is to avoid a situation when a model does not discover patterns but rather learns all examples by heart. The next step is then to train the model using the available data. Then the task is solved on test data and interpreted. The interpretation may vary from one model to another and from one task to another. After the interpretation comes to the step of criticising the model. The goal of criticising is a feedback loop in order to improve the performance of the model.

Figure 2: Abstract ML pipeline.

Figure 3: MLFastSim pipeline.

The MLFastSim workflow follows the same pipeline described above (Figure 3). Based on our knowledge of shower generation we build a VAE, and then we train the model using data from Geant4 which is used as a ground truth. Next, we generate a set of showers sampling from the latent space of VAE. Having two sets of showers, one generated with Geant4 and one generated with VAE, we can evaluate the performance. In order to do that, we calculate observables, i.e. a physical quantity that can be measured or calculated: the longitudinal profile, lateral profile, first and second moments of profiles, total energy, energy per layer and cell energy. Those values are calculated for each shower, so now we can calculate and plot distributions of those values. The performance evaluation is based on comparing the agreement of observable distributions between full simulation and fast simulation.

3 MODEL OPTIMISATION

3.1 Hyperparameters

Machine learning models have trainable parameters, which are adjusted during the training, and hyperparameters, whose value is chosen before a model is trained. The examples of the second ones are the size of a neural network, the learning rate or the batch size. A careful choice of hyperparameters can significantly impact the model’s performance. The value of hyperparameters might differ from task to task, from model to model and from physical device to physical device. Hence, there are no strict and explicit rules on how to choose the value of hyperparameters. Examples of hyperparameters in deep learning models are batch size, learning rate, optimiser type, activation function type, depth or width of the model etc.

To choose the best set of hyperparameter values one can manually experiment with different setups. The biggest drawback of such an approach is the big search space. In order to reduce it,

we use a dedicated software, Optuna, which assists in the choice of hyperparameters by testing only promising values of hyperparameters, not all of them.

3.2 Optuna

Optuna [1] is an open-source framework automating hyperparameter search. We have decided to explore this framework first of all because is robust, up to date and easy to use. Furthermore, it provides various features like easy parallelization or quick visualisation callbacks and adopts state-of-the-art algorithms for sampling hyperparameters.

The implementation of our model is written in TensorFlow using the Keras interface. This is very important for our decision about the choice of the framework since Optuna is lightweight, versatile and platform agnostic which makes it an excellent alternative to work with Keras.

3.3 ML4FastSim framework description

3.3.1 Introduction

Figure 4: The pipeline extended with Optuna.

The initial model was implemented as a standalone object with predefined parameters like a number of hidden layers, a type of activation function, the size of latent space, etc. Therefore we have started with reorganising the model manufacturer.

Currently, the most high-level class which provides an interface to a user is `VAEHandler`. This class is responsible not only for building and compiling a model but also for running training in various modes (see 3.3.3). On the other hand class `VAE` is a `Keras Model` which is used to define the architecture of the model.

Implementation of a handler for a model allowed implementation of a class responsible for hyperparameter tuning, i.e. `HyperparameterTuner`, which is a key component of this project. An object of this class based on parameters like study name, hyperparameters to be tuned, model and data set creates an instance of an Optuna study. The goal of the study is to minimise an objective function which is the validation loss in our case.

As presented in Figure (5), Optuna repeats a four-steps cycle multiple times. One cycle is called a trial. A trial starts with choosing hyperparameters. Optuna offers multiple algorithms responsible for hyperparameter selection, but we have decided to use `TPESampler` which implements TPE (Tree-structured Parzen Estimator) algorithm [12]. The sampler, based on the knowledge of how well performed previous trials were, chooses values of hyperparameters and

then a model is built and compiled with. Then comes a step of training the model, and finally the value of an objective function (final validation loss) is forwarded to a database alongside hyperparameter values.

This procedure is repeated multiple times and after a preset number of trials, we can get the most optimised model with respect to the objective function.

Figure 5: Optuna workflow.

3.3.2 Distribute training

The initial implementation is a single-threaded mode. Since the search space is still huge, one could try to parallelize the process of searching optimal hyperparameters. Fortunately, Optuna provides a very simple API which enables this feature.

We have extended `HyperparameterTuner` class with fields called `study_name` and `storage`. If one runs multiple optimisation procedures referring to the same study name, the optimisation will be performed based on common knowledge. In other words, the common knowledge will be kept in one, common database (e.g. MySQL database). Whenever a trial is complete, the sampler queries the database for a current state of knowledge and based on this information chooses a new set of parameters. When the training is done, Optuna sends the information about the trial performance to the database updating common knowledge.

Figure 6: The pipeline extended with a connection to a database.

3.3.3 K-fold cross validation

Deep learning highly relies on stochasticity. If one runs an experiment twice with the same initial setup, usually the results will differ slightly. The training set is usually shuffled after each epoch so that the model sees training examples in a different order in each epoch (and of course in each experiment). This implies that the results of the experiment should be interpreted as a particular value of a random variable. Hence, the recommended approach is to repeat experiments if possible and average the results. This issue is of course also connected with model performance. It is not recommended to evaluate the quality of the model based on a single training, hence we have extended the pipeline by implementing k-fold cross-validation.

K-fold cross-validation is a standard procedure which splits a data set into K chunks and repeats training and validation procedure K times, but each time a different part of unseen data is used for validation (see Figure (7)). Now one can run training in two different modes. If one specifies more than one K-fold split, then the previously mentioned procedure will be used. Otherwise, the framework will use the constant between 0 and 1, which denotes a fraction of the data set that will be used for validation.

Figure 7: K-fold cross validation scheme [7]. In this example $k = 5$.

Figure 8: The pipeline extended with k-fold cross-validation.

3.3.4 Integration with W&B

Figure 9: Within the W&B project one can perform multiple experiments. Each experiment consists of multiple runs. A run is a single training or k trainings performed in K-fold mode.

Tracking the progress of multiple trainings is a big challenge. Therefore, we augmented ML-FastSim with a tool called Weight&biases (W&B) [14]. The tool can track the metrics, notify

about training crashes, aggregate results into aesthetic tables, generate reports or organise training into sub-projects.

W&B has a very straightforward interface so whenever a new training is going to perform, VAEHandler setups a W&B run. Now the validation loss, total loss and current epoch are live-plotted on the project’s page on the W&B server. Moreover, all the logs printed to the shell are also saved by W&B and, what is most important, the values of the hyperparameters are also saved.

Within one project, one can create multiple experiments. Each run (training) is saved separately. So if you perform a hyperparameter optimisation you can check logs and information about each trial (Figure 10). Finally, with W&B one can straightforwardly create a parallel coordinates plot to combine all runs within an experiment (Figure 11).

Run name	State	Tag	Created*	Runtime	Batch_size	Epochs	Intermediate_loss	Final_loss	Learning_rate	Optimiser_Type	Steps	Final_loss	Val_Final_loss
run00000000	Failed	Hyperparameter	21 apr 20:26	128	500	(1191.2116,208,402)	42	0.00232	Optimiser_Type:ADAM	208	10021.244	24623.771	
run00000001	Failed	Hyperparameter	21 apr 20:42	128	500	(1182.1442,202,612,261)	52	0.00262	Optimiser_Type:SGD	9	NAN	NAN	
run00000002	Failed	Hyperparameter	21 apr 20:36	128	500	(1174.1462,272,307)	77	0.00294	Optimiser_Type:SGD	9	NAN	NAN	
run00000003	Failed	Hyperparameter	21 apr 20:36	128	500	(1183.1438,340,510)	42	0.00296	Optimiser_Type:SGD	9	NAN	NAN	
run00000004	Failed	Hyperparameter	21 apr 20:26	128	500	(1182.4481)	16	0.00246	Optimiser_Type:SGD	9	NAN	NAN	
run00000005	Failed	Hyperparameter	21 apr 20:26	128	500	(1182.4481)	30	0.00255	Optimiser_Type:ADAM	45	10532.489	10233.58	
run00000006	Failed	Hyperparameter	21 apr 20:36	128	500	(1176.1462,380,340)	28	0.00252	Optimiser_Type:SGD	9	NAN	NAN	
run00000007	Failed	Hyperparameter	21 apr 20:36	128	500	(1176.1462,380,340)	85	0.00252	Optimiser_Type:ADAM	89	10488.088	10672.631	
run00000008	Failed	Hyperparameter	21 apr 20:36	128	500	(1195.1462,320)	85	0.00229	Optimiser_Type:ADAM	129	14437.561	14482.412	

Figure 10: A table of runs within one experiment.

Figure 11: A parallel coordinates plot of hyperparameter tuning.

4 UPGRADES AND NEXT-LEVEL ADD-ONS

With the development of a framework for hyperparameter tuning, we also impacted other aspects of the MLFastSim. These improvements are made to make the MLFastSim solution scalable, robust and high-quality software.

4.1 Python Enhancement Proposals 8 style guide

The Python Enhancement Proposals 8 (PEP-8) is a document that provides guidelines and best practices on how to write Python code. The primary focus of PEP-8 is to improve the readability and consistency of Python code.

The first step that we achieved was to rename all variables according to PEP-8 recommendations, then we added docstrings, reorganised the structure of the project, optimised imports, removed obsolete code, wrap redundant code into functions, etc.

4.2 YAPF

Using code formatters like YAPF [6] or Black [2] highly increases the readability of the code. Decision on formatting a code according to one, the concrete style allows keeping code consistent and harmonious.

We have decided to format the code with YAPF. See the example result below.

```
while(energyParticle<=variables.max_energy):
    # scale the energy of each cell to the energy of the primary particle (in MeV units)
    events = np.array(h5['%s'%energyParticle])/(energyParticle*1000)
    energies_Train.append( events.reshape(len(events), variables.original_dim) )
    # build the energy and angle condition vectors
    condE_Train.append( [energyParticle/variables.max_energy]*len(events) )
    condAngle_Train.append( [angleParticle/variables.max_angle]*len(events) )
    # build the geometry condition vector (1 hot encoding vector)
    if( geo == 'SiW' ):
        condGeo_Train.append( [[0,1]]*len(events) )
    if( geo == 'SciPb' ):
        condGeo_Train.append( [[1,0]]*len(events) )
    energyParticle *=2
```

Figure 12: Before applying YAPF.

```
while (energyParticle <= variables.max_energy):
    # scale the energy of each cell to the energy of the primary particle (in MeV units)
    events = np.array(h5['%s' % energyParticle]) / (energyParticle * 1000)
    energies_Train.append(events.reshape(len(events), variables.original_dim))
    # build the energy and angle condition vectors
    condE_Train.append([energyParticle / variables.max_energy] * len(events))
    condAngle_Train.append([angleParticle / variables.max_angle] * len(events))
    # build the geometry condition vector (1 hot encoding vector)
    if (geo == 'SiW'):
        condGeo_Train.append([[0, 1]] * len(events))
    if (geo == 'SciPb'):
        condGeo_Train.append([[1, 0]] * len(events))
    energyParticle *= 2
```

Figure 13: After applying YAPF.

4.3 Type annotations

Python is a dynamic programming language which means that information about a type of variable is not necessary while running the code. This approach might increase the work speed of researchers but on the other hand, reduces the readability of the code. Detailed information about types accepted by a function allows not only avoids some bugs, but a sophisticated IDE can suggest what kind of parameters should a researcher pass to the function or what the expected type of returned value is.

We have annotated some of the existing files. This practice is definitely recommended to create a big software.

4.4 Requirements file

We have added a file which lists the required packages to use the repository. The packages can be easily installed with `pip install -r requirements.txt`. As of the day of 24/08/2022, the required packages for MLFastSim are:

```
tensorflow==2.9.1
numpy==1.23.1
```



```

h5py==3.7.0
matplotlib==3.5.2
optuna==2.10.1
mysqlclient==2.1.1
pymysql==1.0.2
scikit-learn==1.1.1
scipy==1.8.1
wandb==0.13.1

```

4.5 Upgraded code to use TensorFlow 2.9

By the end of June 2022, the repository was using TensorFlow 2.4. With small changes, we adjusted the code so that it can be run with a newer version - 2.9.

4.6 Logic for GPU usage management

We are aware that the model's training demands a substantial amount of GPU resources. Parallelization can significantly speed up training time when multiple GPU units are available in the machine. Therefore, we have added logic for GPU usage management. The main class, `GPULimiter`, can create multiple logical GPU units and limit the maximum memory usage. This enables the creation of an environment for parallel computation. Next, the class can instantiate a `MirroredStrategy`, which distributes the training process across multiple GPU units by duplicating the model and weights. After each training step, the model's weights are collected and unified to obtain a single instance of the model. Finally, the class can build and compile the initial TensorFlow model within the `MirroredStrategy` scope. From this moment, the model is ready to be trained in a distributed environment.

5 FURTHER RESEARCH

The project is very broad, promising and exciting so many other directions of further research have been discussed with the supervisors and Jean-Roch Vilmant. Below we describe some of the vague ideas, which require further investigation.

- Currently, `HyperparameterTuner` uses `VAEHandler`. As a next step, one could create an abstract class `ModelHandler` from which the `VAEHandler` inherits which would increase the scalability of `HyperparameterTuner`. Then the `HyperparameterTuner` could be used to tune an arbitrary model (for which a researcher would provide a handler).
- As mentioned in section 2.2 currently the validation process relies on the comparison of observable distributions. This idea is to incorporate the difference between the distributions into the loss function. We propose to estimate the probability distribution function of an observable using kernel density estimation [13]. Then for each step of the training procedure, generate a small number of showers, calculate the observable and using the likelihood function estimate how likely it is, that a generated shower comes from a ground truth distribution.
- One could consider adding an extra term to the loss function consisting of reconstruction loss (binary cross-entropy) and validation loss (Kullback-Leibler divergence), which will be an L_2 distance between the reconstructed shower and the original shower.

- Since ultimately the shower is a multidimensional image, one could consider the usage of convolutional layers in the encoder and the decoder instead of dense layers. However, it is worth mentioning that this approach arises the problem of passing meta-parameters (geometry of a calorimeter, initial energy and initial angle of a particle) to the model. Currently, we just concatenate them with a flattened shower, but while using convolutional layers, one needs to provide a more robust solution.
- Flow-based generative models are an interesting approach because they are constructed by a sequence of invertible transformations. The such model explicitly learns directly the data distribution and therefore the loss function is simply the negative log-likelihood. One could try flow-based VAE [10] [9] in our use case.
- Erik Buchman et al [4] suggest extending their generative model by an additional part called the corrector. The corrector is located after the generator and is responsible for amending the generated or reconstructed showers. We believe that this idea is worth further investigation into our problem.
- The task we address using MLFastSim is known as conditional generative modelling. Given specific conditions, the model is tasked with generating a particular shower.

Drawing inspiration from [15], we propose an extension to the standard VAE through the inclusion of a multilayer perceptron module (refer to Figure (14)). This module would be accountable for generating an embedding of conditions, including the geometry of a calorimeter, initial energy, and initial angle of a particle. We anticipate that this approach could enhance the model's robustness.

Figure 14: A model architecture with MLP used to encode metaparameters.

- [3] [5] show that validation loss (Kullback-Leibler divergence) highly overweight the reconstruction loss in the early stages of the training, but after the behaviour is reversed. The idea of the active weighting of losses would fix the problem.
- Currently, the input to the tuner is specified in `tune_model.py` file. Moving the input to a JSON would be a better way to simplify changes between experiments.
- Currently, in the k-folding, each fold could be run on an independent thread. Although the idea seems to be promising, we identify two problems with this approach. Firstly, each fold requires access to a dataset. Duplication of the dataset will consume a lot of memory which is unacceptable. Secondly, it is hard to gather the results from each fold. The Optuna optimisation procedure is run on a CPU but the training is performed on GPU. This means that one would need to start multiple GPU processes. This task seems to be nontrivial, bearing in mind that this method should be executed within the Optuna run.

6 SUMMARY

In this report, we presented important extensions that have been added to the project during the summer internship. Now, MLFastSim offers also the setup for the distributed hyperparameter tuning, k-fold cross-validation, tracking training progress with W&B and highly scalable validation procedure.

Moreover, we improved the readability of the project by formatting the code, annotating methods and functions with types and aligning the project code style with a stand-alone style guide. We upgraded the code to use a newer version of TensorFlow and built a logic responsible for GPU usage management. Finally, we identified many areas where further research can be conducted.

The code repository is publicly available[11].

7 REFERENCES

- [1] Takuya Akiba et al. “25th ACM SIGKDD International Conference on Knowledge Discovery and Data Mining”. In: (2019).
- [2] *Black*. *The Uncompromising Code Formatter*. URL: <https://github.com/psf/black> (visited on 08/24/2022).
- [3] Samuel R. Bowman et al. “Generating Sentences from a Continuous Space”. In: *SIGNLL Conference on Computational Natural Language Learning (CONLL)* (2016).
- [4] Erik Buhmann et al. “Getting High: High Fidelity Simulation of High Granularity Calorimeters with High Speed”. In: *Computing and Software for Big Science* 5 (2021), p. 13.
- [5] Irina Higgins et al. “beta-VAE: Learning Basic Visual Concepts with a Constrained Variational Framework”. In: *International Conference on Learning Representations (ICLR)* (2017).
- [6] Daniel Jasper. *YAPF. A formatter for Python files*. URL: <https://github.com/google/yapf> (visited on 08/24/2022).
- [7] *K-fold cross validation image*. URL: <https://www.section.io/engineering-education/how-to-implement-k-fold-cross-validation/5-fold-cv.jpeg> (visited on 08/25/2022).
- [8] Diederik P. Kingma and Max Welling. “Auto-Encoding Variational Bayes”. In: *International Conference on Learning Representations (ICLR)* (2017).
- [9] Diederik P. Kingma et al. “Improving Variational Inference with Inverse Autoregressive Flow”. In: *International Conference on Neural Information Processing Systems* (2016).
- [10] Danilo Jimenez Rezende and Shakir Mohamed. “Variational Inference with Normalizing Flows”. In: *International Conference on Machine Learning* (2015).
- [11] Dalila Salamani, Anna Zaborowska, and Maciej Draguła. *MLFastSim: an open-source framework for optimisation design of fast simulation models*. URL: <https://github.com/DalilaSalamani/MLFastSim> (visited on 08/25/2022).
- [12] *TPESampler*. URL: <https://optuna.readthedocs.io/en/stable/reference/generated/optuna.samplers.TPESampler.html> (visited on 08/25/2022).

- [13] Jake Vanderplas. *Kernel Density Estimation*. URL: <https://scikit-learn.org/stable/modules/density.html> (visited on 08/23/2022).
- [14] *Weights & Biases - the machine learning platform for developers to build better models faster*. 2018. URL: <https://wandb.ai/site>.
- [15] Maciej Wołczyk et al. “PluGeN: Multi-Label Conditional Generation From Pre-Trained Models”. In: (2022).

